

Digitizing cultural heritage through a decision support tool: Lighting design of the neoclassical buildings.

Stelios Zerefos

*Professor, School of Applied Arts, Hellenic Open University, Patras, Greece,
email: zerefos@eap.gr*

Thanos Balafoutis

*Researcher, School of Applied Arts, Hellenic Open University, Patras, Greece,
email: balafoutis.athanasios@ac.eap.gr*

Gerasimos Vonitsanos

*Researcher, School of Applied Arts, Hellenic Open University, Patras, Greece,
email: mvonitsanos@eap.gr*

Abstract: This research presents evidence of lighting design decisions through a decision support system for the illumination of the facades of neoclassical buildings. The proposed system is based on a novel methodology for lighting neoclassical buildings. The methodology starts with the collection of the most important decorative and architectural elements on facades of neoclassical buildings and filters them to find shared elements. Each element is lit with different types of luminaires in various mounting positions and tested by lighting simulation software to create a database of lighting results. The research is also concentrated on the development of a robust web-platform for modeling Heterogeneous and Semi-Structured lighting design data using a relational database. This database can be used to analyze similarities and differences between identical element types in different buildings, identify architectural “preferences” concerning the elements used in each case, detect common elements in various building uses or the use of different elements in similar types of uses, and in general constitute a valuable tool when researching any aspect of the facades of neoclassical buildings.

1. Introduction

Studying antiquity was the key, according to the Enlightenment [1], for humanity to approach integration. Scholars from the French Academy in Rome [2] have established in the 1740s the neoclassical language. During the same period Piranesi’s influence over architects of the neo-classical movement and the discovery of the ruins of Herculaneum (1738) and Pompeii (1748) had a defining impact on Neoclassicism [3]. Nowadays, many of the neoclassical buildings that stand the test of time are characterized as "historical" and constitute part of the living memory of a place at a given timeframe [4].

Historical buildings are classified into architectural periods that can be defined by their typology and the diversity of the morphological elements on their façades. The architectural periods demonstrate greater diversity than any methodology would attempt to group them and this term is now used to categorize and analyze buildings with common standard features, cultural trends depending on the socio-economic factors of the construction period, movements or ideologies. Lighting these types of buildings can be a difficult and complex task due to the vast number of different elements that have to be taken into account, as well as the highly sculptured surfaces that make it very difficult to imagine lighting and shadow results.

2. Scope and Methodology

This research aims to present a lighting design methodology through a digitized database. This database works as a decision support tool for lighting neoclassical buildings, by showing lighting results of different lighting combinations by different light sources in different positions, lighting a multitude of three-dimensional elements. Based on the fact that neoclassical buildings can be defined by repeated sets of distinct morphological and decorative elements found on their facades [5], these elements are recorded and categorized in a vast collection of 150 listed buildings across the Globe (*Fig. 1*), so as to create a worldwide database with facade characteristics of neoclassical buildings [6] [7]. This is achieved through the analysis of the general structure of the buildings in question, by studying grouped structural elements such as the base, the body, the coronation but also overhangs and openings.

WORKSHOP

“Historic Cities & ICT: Which building will you save first?”

Fig. 1. The 150 selected neoclassical buildings around the world.

The methodology starts with the collection of the most important decorative and architectural elements on facades of neoclassical buildings [8] [9] and filters them to find shared elements (Fig.2). The facades are then procedurally decomposed into modules according to the collection of three-dimensional elements and each module is lit and tested through lighting simulations [10] by different types of luminaires (Fig.3) and various mounting positions (Fig.4).

Fig. 2. Identification of the architectural elements.

Fig. 3. Different beam types of luminaires.

Table 1. Lighting fixtures.

Category	#	Description	Lumen	Category	#	Description	Lumen
Floodlights	A1	Light Blade Spot	390lm	Linear Lights	B1	Spot Angle (8°)	541lm
	A2	Narrow Spot (12°)	2450lm		B5	Spot Angle (8°)	1082lm
	A3	Flood Spot (38°)	2600lm		B6	Spot Angle (8°)	2163lm
	A4	Wide Flood Spot (52°)	1850lm		B2	Flood Angle (32°)	541lm
	A5	Narrow Spot (10°)	850lm		B7	Flood Angle (32°)	1082lm
	A6	Flood Spot (34°)	850lm		B8	Flood Angle (32°)	2163lm
	C1	Narrow Spot	1470lm		B3	Wall Grazing	2370lm
	C2	Spot	3780lm		B9	Wall Grazing	1180lm
C3	Spot	3780lm	B4		Flood Angle (44°)	2370lm	
C4	Wide Flood	3780lm	B10		Flood Angle (44°)	1180lm	

Fig. 4. Mounting positions on different elements.

The type of luminaires and the mounting positions used have been selected through observation of the vast majority of lit historical buildings. The simulations then form the database of possible lighting scenarios, which are scrutinized by experts in the field of lighting design. Finally, the results that correspond to the preferences of lighting experts (Fig.5) are classified and present a number of different methods on how to light the façade of a historical building [11] depending on the lighting source characteristics, its position and more importantly the element that is lit.

WORKSHOP

"Historic Cities & ICT: Which building will you save first?"

Fig. 5. Simulated results.

WORKSHOP
 "Historic Cities & ICT: Which building will you save first?"

3. Development of the database

As mentioned before our research is also concentrated on the development of a robust web-platform for modeling Heterogeneous and Semi-Structured lighting design data using a relational database. This particular type of database is used primarily to store data sub-divided into groups known as tables. The technology mentioned above is particularly significant for this case study as it meets different requirements of a large number of data, independently of their structure.

The large number of collected files regarding lighting design features and the heterogeneity between them led to the conclusion that they had to be preceded by an initialization that divided them into small groups and then processed more efficiently. The files were then grouped into different categories, depending on their lighting design data. In the current development, we focused on the application itself and not only on the data and their relational theories. The method of modeling by query was used and led us to the creation of specific database tables, containing only the required data, giving the ability to make the aggregations efficiently. Finally these tables as active pre-built result sets contained only the data needed to present.

4. The database

All of this research was organized in a web application for the dissemination of its results. The application was set up as a web page through the Hellenic Open University server at <http://lhb.eap.gr/> and can be used in any electronic device (PC, laptop, tablet, smartphone etc).

Fig. 6. Home page.

The user can initially read information on historical elements of the architectural period being explored (Fig. 7), and by selecting a building from the list of 150 buildings that were analyzed to categorize the building elements, it describes essential information such as the title, the address, construction start dates - completion and the architect who designed the building (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Page of the historical data.

Fig. 8. Building selected.

In addition to the above, next to each building, a list of the morphological elements that comprise its facades is displayed. This provides the user with a first contact with the three-dimensional elements of the database. The category "Methodology" (Fig.9), in the main menu of the application, makes it easy to select and view different parts of the research. This category is considered the precursor of the database, as the user can get all the information needed to be properly guided in the search. From there it is possible to familiarize with the morphological and decorative elements through images that make them easier to visually understand (Fig.10).

Fig. 9. Selection of the methodology in the application.

Fig. 10. Page of the morphological and decorative elements.

The «Database» option, introduces the user to the database. From here, different options (filters) initially appear, which give the user, the possibility to select specific characteristics. These relate to the type of lighting characteristics, photometrical data and many other categories according to Table 2.

Table 2. Database options.

	Filters	Specific Characteristics
A	Basic Categories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Volume lighting, - Horizontal elements lighting, - Vertical elements lighting, - Decorative elements lighting, - Openings lighting
B	Lighting Effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accent Lighting, - Down Lighting, - Floodlighting, - Silhouetting, - Up Lighting, - Wall Washer, - Wall Grazing
C	Elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decorative elements, - Openings, - Balconies & Balconette, - Corbelling, - Columns & Pilasters, - Domes, - Niches, - Parapets & Podiums, - Surface & Rustication, - Statues & Sculptures, - Groups, - Plans
D	Lighting Fixtures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Light Blade Spot, - Narrow Spot (8o - 12o), - Spot (13o - 30o), - Flood Spot (31o - 45o), - Wide Flood Spot (46o - 60o), - Linear Light (Spot Angle), - Linear Light (Flood Angle), - Linear Light (Wall Grazing)
E	Photometrical Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reflection Factors, - Color Temperature

Fig. 11. The database.

Fig. 12. Feature selection through filters.

By choosing some filters, the application presents the results of those closest to the options selected. The more filters are selected, the more specialized the search is. The optical results presented, bear a general title of the typology of the elements concerned, and then, through codification¹, inform about the type of the luminaires, the mounting position of the luminaires and the color temperature (*Fig.13*). If the user selects the image, a new page shows the result with detailed information on the characteristics of the luminaire and the position of installation (*Fig.14*).

Fig. 13. Results of the database.

¹ The codification consists of four segments. The name of the morphological element (e.g., Balcony), the lighting fixture (e.g., A2), the position of the installation of the luminaire (e.g., D4) and the color temperature (e.g., 3000K).

Fig. 14. Characteristics of the results.

Another possibility is that of the registration; experts in lighting design can apply to register and have an impact on the evaluation of the results. Experts will be sent a password to be able to enroll in the application. The capabilities they will have are that they can evaluate each result according to a score scale displayed only to them, and that they will receive updates on any additions. At the same time, non-registered users of the application will be able to see the average of the evaluation of each result. In the future, a blog can be created within the application, which can be discussed on relevant topics. Finally a contact form enables it to anyone who wants to get in touch with application administrators (Fig.15).

Fig. 15. Registration and contact form.

4. Conclusions

This research shows that there is further scope into researching lighting design methods for historical buildings and providing a portfolio of lighting solutions to the designers. Evidence from this research provides promising results for the verification of the proposed methodology. The database can be used also to identify

predominant neoclassical features of buildings throughout the world and can be categorized and used in a multitude of aspects, from defining the most probable element or group of elements to be found on a specific timeframe, to identifying the most important neoclassical features in a specific country. Further work on this methodology can involve the study of buildings from different architectural periods.

5. References

- [1] M. Horkheimer, T. Adorno. "The Dialectic of Enlightenment. New York". Herder and Herder. 1972.
- [2] D. Watkin. "A History of Western Architecture". London. Laurence King Publishing. 1986.
- [3] B. Fletcher. "Sir Banister Fletcher's: History of Architecture (Twentieth Edition)". Architectural Press. 1996.
- [4] T. Balafoutis, S. Zerefos. "Designing lighting for historical buildings using a modular methodology: The case of the work of Ernst Ziller in Greece". In: Proceedings of the Balkan Light Conference. (Athens, Greece). 2015.
- [5] A. Stratton. "Elements of Form and Design in Classic Architecture". Jeremy Mills Publishing. 2007.
- [6] T. Balafoutis, S. Zerefos. "A Database of Architectural Details: The case of Neoclassical Elements and Ornaments". In: Proceedings of the 4th Biennial of Architectural and Urban Restoration, BRAU4. (Piraeus, Greece). 2018.
- [7] J. Summerson. "The Classical Language of Architecture". The MIT Press. 1992.
- [8] O. Hopkins. "Reading Architecture – A Visual Lexicon". Laurence King Publishing. 2012.
- [9] F. S. Meyer. "Handbook of Ornament". Dover Publications. 1957.
- [10] T. Balafoutis, S. Zerefos. "Lighting Design Simulation Programs Comparison". In: EinB2017–6th International Conference "ENERGY in BUILDINGS 2017". (Athens, Greece). 2017.
- [11] T. Balafoutis, S. Zerefos. "Developing a Toolset for Decision-Making on the Design of Lighting for Historical Buildings". In: The International Journal of Architectonic, Spatial, and Environmental Design, Volume 12, Issue 2, 2018. Article: pp.15–39.
- [12] A. Badia, D. Lemire. "A call to arms: Revisiting database design". SIGMOD Record, 40(3):61–69, 2011.
- [13] A. Schram, K. M. Anderson. "Mysql to nosql: Data modeling challenges in supporting scalability". In Conference on Systems, Pro-gramming, and Applications: Software for Humanity (SPLASH), pages191–202, 2012.

WORKSHOP

"Historic Cities & ICT: Which building will you save first?"

